

ABSTRACTS of the

**7th Meeting of the European Section
and
8th Meeting of the North American Section
of the
International Academy of Cardiovascular
Sciences (IACS)**

Banja Luka, 20-23 September 2021

Organised by:

International Academy of Cardiovascular Sciences (IACS) – European and North American Sections

University of Banja Luka, the Republic of Srpska, Bosnia & Herzegovina

Faculty of Medicine, University of Banja Luka, the Republic of Srpska, Bosnia & Herzegovina

Serbian Association of Arteriosclerosis, Trombosis and Vascular Biology Research, Belgrade, Serbia

Association for Atherosclerosis and Cardiovascular Research, Banja Luka,
the Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Meeting Committees

Presidency

RANKO ŠKRBIĆ, Chair

MILOŠ P STOJILJKOVIĆ, Co-Chair

International Organising & Programme Committee

ROBERTO BOLLI, President, IACS (Louisville, KY, USA)

NARANJAN S DHALLA, Founder and CEO, IACS (Winnipeg, MB, Canada)

GARY LOPASCHUK, President, North American Section, IACS (Edmonton, AB, Canada)

BOHUSLAV OŠTÁDAL, Past president, IACS (Prague, Czech Republic)

GRANT N PIERCE, President-Elect, IACS (Winnipeg, MB, Canada)

ANDRAS VARRO, President, European Section, IACS (Szeged, Hungary)

International Programme Committee

Devendra K Agrawal, Pomona, CA, USA

Istvan Baczkó, Szeged, Hungary

Monika Barteková, Bratislava, Slovakia

Maciej Banach, Łódź, Poland

Jerzy Beltowski, Lubin, Poland

Roberto Bolli, Louisville, KY, USA

Tonino Bombardini, Pisa, Italy

Harpal S Buttar, Ottawa, ON, Canada

Michael Czubryt, Winnipeg, MB, Canada

Buddhadeb Dawn, Las Vegas, NV, USA

Naranjan S Dhalla, Winnipeg, MB, Canada

Sanjiv Dhingra, Winnipeg, MB, Canada

Mirza Dilić, Sarajevo, Bosnia & Herzegovina

Dragan M Djuric, Belgrade, Serbia

Igor Efimov, Washington, DC, USA

Brent M Egan, Greenville, SC, USA

Peter Ferdinandy, Budapest, Hungary

Ferenc Gallyas, Pécs, Hungary

Vladimir L Jakovljevic, Kragujevac, Serbia

Ana Jerončić, Split, Croatia

Lorrie A Kirshenbaum, Winnipeg, MB, CA

Rakesh C. Kukreja, Richmond, VA, USA

Vincenzo Lionetti, Pisa, Italy

Gary Lopaschuk, Edmonton, AB, Canada

Martin Morad, Charleston, SC, USA

Danina Muntean, Timisoara, Romania

Bohuslav Oštádal, Prague, Czech Republic

Petr Oštádal, Prague, Czech Republic

Miodrag Ć Ostojić, Belgrade, Serbia

Zoltan Papp, Debrecen, Hungary

Grant N Pierce, Winnipeg, MB, Canada

Tanya Ravingerova, Bratislava, Slovakia

Alan P Robertson, Ames, IA, USA

Dineder Singla, Orlando, FL, USA

Jan Slezak, Bratislava, Slovakia

Šekib Sokolović, Sarajevo, Bos.-Herzegovina

Paramjit Tappia, Winnipeg, MB, Canada

Srinivas Tipparaju, Tampa, FL, USA

Gregor Tratar, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Belma Turan, Ankara, Turkey

Suresh C Tyagi, Louisville, KY, USA

Andras Varro, Szeged, Hungary

Nathan D Wong, Irvine, CA, USA

Local Programme and CME Planning Committee

Branko Beleslin, Belgrade, Serbia

Dragan M Djuric, Belgrade, Serbia

Ana Đorđević-Dikić, Belgrade, Serbia

Ljiljana C Gojković-Bukarica, Belgrade, SRB

Vladimir L Jakovljevic, Kragujevac, Serbia

Nina Japundžić-Žigon, Belgrade, Serbia

Katarina S Lalić, Belgrade, Serbia

Nebojša M Lalić, Belgrade, Serbia

Goran Lončar, Belgrade, Serbia

Dragana Lončar-Stojiljković, Belgrade, Serbia

Amela Matavulj, Banja Luka, RS, BA

Momir M Mikov, Novi Sad, Serbia

Milan Milojević, Belgrade, Serbia

Zoran Miloradović, Belgrade, Serbia

Milan A Nedeljković, Belgrade, Serbia

Lana Nežić, Banja Luka, RS, BA

Miodrag Ć Ostojić, Belgrade, Serbia

Petar Otašević, Belgrade, Serbia

Miodrag Perić, Belgrade, Serbia

Nenad Ponorac, Banja Luka, RS, BA

Miroslav Radenković, Belgrade, Serbia

Tatjana Simić, Belgrade, Serbia

Tanja Šobot, Banja Luka, RS, BA

Svjetlana Stoisavljević-Šatara, BL, RS, BA

Nataša Stojaković, Banja Luka, RS, BA

Miloš P Stojiljković, Banja Luka, RS, BA

Ranko Škrbić, Banja Luka, RS, BA

Nebojša M Tasić, Belgrade, Serbia

Zoran Todorović, Belgrade, Serbia

Duško Vulić, Banja Luka, RS, BA

Local Organising Committee

Đorđe Đukanović, Banja Luka

Ana Golić, Banja Luka

Milkica Grabež

Žana M Maksimović, Banja Luka

Nataša Miljuš, Banja Luka

Sonja Trbojević, Banja Luka

Pharmacogenetic Biomarkers in Personalized Therapy of Cardiovascular Diseases

Karmen Stankov,¹ Aleksandar Redžek,² Momir Mikov,³ Ljiljana Rakićević,⁴ Dragica Radojković,⁴ Lazar Velicki,² Dejan Sakač,² Bojan Stanimirov,¹ Nebojša Pavlović⁵

Abstract

The successful completion of the human genome project and advances in genomic knowledge and technology enabled the implementation of personalized medicine in clinical practice. Multiple types of variants affect gene function and individual drug response. Cardiovascular (CV) diseases are the leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, despite considerable advances in CV pharmacology. Thus it is important to use pharmacogenetic (PG) biomarkers to select the right drug, its adequate dose for the individual patient at the right time, maximizing the efficacy and minimizing adverse drug reactions (ADR). Strong and consistent evidence suggests associations of genomic variants with clopidogrel effectiveness after percutaneous coronary intervention, warfarin dose requirements and statin tolerability. Our main aim is to further elucidate the value of pre-emptive PG testing to guide CV therapies and to emphasize the significance of PG biomarkers application in CV pharmacology for prediction of ADR, such as statin-induced myopathy or a hemorrhage/thrombosis event during anticoagulant and antiplatelet therapy. Analysis of regulatory agencies guidelines and results of clinical trials revealed the PG biomarkers that are added to drug labels of many commonly prescribed drugs in CV pharmacology. The results of our analysis show that pre-emptive genotyping prior to therapy and implementation of therapeutic guidelines that involve PG biomarkers represent the step forward towards the personalized approach in CV pharmacology. According to results of analysis we may conclude that it is clinically recommended to apply the PG biomarkers in order to individualize the warfarin and clopidogrel doses and to improve the efficacy and safety profile. Pharmacogenomics offers tools that can revolutionize drug design and clinical trials and make both more economically efficient. Further advances in cardiovascular PG biomarkers research using artificial intelligence and machine learning techniques may improve implementation of personalized medicine principles in therapy of hypertension, arrhythmias and chemotherapy-induced cardiomyopathy in close future.

Acknowledgment: Supported by Project of special interest for sustainable development in the Autonomous Province of Vojvodina No. 142-451-2283/2021-01/02, and Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development, Republic of Serbia, Grant III41012.

Key words: Pharmacogenetic biomarkers; Personalized therapy; Cardiovascular diseases.

Reference: 1. Duarte JD, Cavallari LH. Pharmacogenetics to guide cardiovascular drug therapy. *Nat Rev Cardiol* 2021 Sep;18(9):649-65. 2. Magavern EF, Kaski JC, Turner RM, Drexel H, Janmohamed A, Scourfield A, et al. The role of pharmacogenomics in contemporary cardiovascular therapy: a position statement from the European Society of Cardiology Working Group on Cardiovascular Pharmacotherapy. *Eur Heart J Cardiovasc Pharmacother* 2021 Feb 26;pvab018. doi: 10.1093/ehjcvp/pvab018. 3. Stankov K, Stanimirov B, Mikov M. Pharmacogenomic determinants of response to cardiovascular drugs. *Med Pregl* 2015 Jul-Aug;68(7-8):259-65.

- (1) Department of Biochemistry, Medical Faculty, University of Novi Sad, Serbia.
- (2) Institute of Cardiovascular diseases of Vojvodina, Medical Faculty, University of Novi Sad, Serbia.
- (3) Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Medical Faculty, University of Novi Sad, Serbia.
- (4) Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering, University of Belgrade, Serbia.
- (5) Department of Pharmacy, Medical Faculty, University of Novi Sad, Serbia.

Correspondence:
KARMEN STANKOV
E: karmen.stankov@mf.uns.ac.rs

ABSTRACT INFO

Abstract ID: 112
Submitted: September 3, 2021